

Future Ocean Observation Drifter (FOOD)

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Introduction

Drifting buoys have been regularly deployed in the ocean since the early 1980s and the setting up of the Argos localization and transmission system. Initially, they sent back Localisation and SST measurements. These were used by National Weather Providers to improve their forecasting capabilities.

With the advent of GPS and its availability for non military purposes, GPS receivers were added to the buoys to improve their Localisation. Furthermore, barometers also started being included on the buoys, increasing their usefulness for meteorological forecasting. Finally, in 2015, new buoys using the American Iridium constellation started to be deployed, enabling near real time data transmission. By early 2017, the vast majority of the drifting buoy network had transitioned to the Iridium network.

The current design of the SVP-B (Sybrandt et al, 2009), the workhorse of the DBCP network (Figure 1), is very plastic heavy, with the buoy hull measuring 40 cm in diameter and made out of acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS). Most buoys last about 18 months and are never recovered, meaning that they are a substantial source of plastic pollution, an issue that has been a growing concern amongst funders and deployers.

The second limitation is the overreliance on a single transmission provider, namely iridium. Any issue with the system would mean the loss of data globally, with no current backup solution.

Figure 1: Standard SVP-B buoy

In order to try and address these 2 issues, in 2022, E-surfmar asked CLS to develop further a wooden buoy prototype it had developed in the framework of an ESA project. This prototype used the Argos/Kineis constellation for data transmission and included a GPS. The aim was to perform preliminary tests in a laboratory and then deploy it in a protected enclosure in Britany.

The next step was to include an environmental sensor on the buoy. To this end, a second prototype with an SST sensor was developed and it was decided that it should be deployed in the open seas to test the design's resilience in real ocean conditions.

Objectives

Faced with the challenge of testing the prototype in the open seas, CLS applied for support from EMSO. The application was successful and CLS was able to deploy the prototype off Villanova in Spain and validate its new platform. The main objective was to test a new type of sea surface ocean drifter for the collection of environmental data. To this end, CLS built a wooden buoy drifter prototype, equipped with a temperature sensor as well as a Argos modem and a GPS. This enabled the retrieval of environmental data as well as technical data such as battery usage. The drifter was deployed at the EMSO OBSEA facility, operated by UPC, in order to investigate its robustness and survivability in real open sea conditions and evaluate the effectiveness of the transmission strategy. CLS chose the EMSO OBSEA facility due to its proximity and the equipment available. Furthermore, CLS had already worked in the past with UPC staff which facilitated communication. In particular, the exposed nature of the deployment site and the presence of meteorological sensors were of particular importance as CLS needed to know the ocean conditions during the duration of the deployment.

Methodology

The first deployment took place on the 10th April 2024 and lasted 75 days after which the buoy broke free. Fortunately, it washed ashore in Villanova and was still transmitting (Figure 2 and 3). This enabled the UPC team to recover the buoy on the 26th June 2024 and assess the damage.

Figure 2: Wooden Buoy attached to the UPC permanent mooring

The examination of the buoy showed only minor damage, with a small crack in the hull. This was patched up with nautical sealant and it was decided to replace the batteries in order to extend its autonomy. Before redeploying it. The second deployment took place on 26th October 2024 and lasted 119 days. The buoy broke loose on 7th December and drifted eastward. It stopped transmitting on 20th February 2025, between the island of Majorca and Sardinia.

Figure 3: Trajectory of the buoy after breaking loose on 7th December 2025

Results

The first deployment enabled the team to validate the design and confirmed the good performance of the buoy's instruments, namely the GPS, the temperature sensor and the Kineis modem and antenna. The recovery following the first beaching also highlighted the buoy's resilience to repeated impacts as it washed ashore a rocky coastline. There was some minor damage with a crack in the hull as well as the ingress of a small amount of sea water but not enough to damage the electronics components including the batteries. The reconditioning prior to the second deployment confirmed the ease of reuse of the platform and in particular the simplicity of changing the batteries. The caulking, which was done using an commercially available product, was very straightforward and could be done locally, without having to ship the buoy back to the manufacturer. The second deployment lasted 119 days with 84 days of drifting sometimes in busy ship lanes. The platform performed well, with regular data transmissions. The exact cause of the loss of transmission cannot be known for certain. This could be the result of damage to the antenna following a collision or due to water entering the buoy and damaging the electronics or due to the buoy being picked up. As the buoy was lost within a regular shipping lane (Figure 3), it is quite possible that the loss was the result of a collision.

Figure 4: along track wave significant wave height for the second deployment

The wave conditions experienced by the buoy (Figure 4) were typical of winter conditions with the significant wave height often exceeding 6 meters, highlighting the buoy’s robustness. It is worth noting that on both deployments, the mooring line was cut, most probably by the propellers of a passing vessel. This suggests that for similar tests, some form of large protective cage could be installed to ensure that the platform is recovered at the end of the trials. Indeed, the total loss of the buoy means that it is not possible to determine the exact cause of failure. In total, the platform was deployed for over 6 months (194 days), proving the robustness of the Woodhull design.

Conclusions and Future work

The EMSO ERIC funding stream enabled CLS to deploy its wooden platform prototype. The support of the local team from UPC meant that it was possible to recover the buoy after 75 days following its beaching and subsequently redeploy the buoy after some minor repairs. All in all, the buoy spent over 6 months at sea, validating the use of wood in drifting buoys as an alternative to plastic. The FOOD project enabled the successful demonstration of the use of wood as an alternative to plastics for drifting buoys.

Future work will focus on turning the prototype into an industrial design enabling the manufacture of standardized units. This also means redesigning the electronics in order to simplify the assembly and lower the costs.

The addition of a barometer to the buoy is also being considered as the National Weather Providers require Sea level Pressure for their daily forecasts. This is particularly challenging as the barometer must be in contact with the outside air but not with any water which would impact on the measurements and also degrade the electronics.

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References

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